

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE CRUCIAL ROLE OF MENTAL MAPPING FOR REINFORCING COGNITIVE AND METACOGNITIVE PROCESSES ON READING COMPREHENSION

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The research is performed in the frame of the the thesis covering the following topic "The Proficiency of Cognitive and Metacognitive Strategies for Developing Learner's Reading Skills"

Abstract

It's a well-acknowledged fact, that among the four key skills for language learning (listening, speaking, reading, writing) reading plays a special role. Reading ability goes beyond the strictly linguistic plane and takes in a process of text interpretation, from decoding and linguistic comprehension to evaluation. Both cognitive and metacognitive strategies go hand in hand to provide successful comprehension, the former helps students to construct meaning while the latter guides, regulates and evaluates. The paper reports research findings of teaching reading through mental mapping, embracing cognitive and metacognitive strategies. Adopting the mind-mapping method our study examines how student's schemata affect the usage of cognitive and metacognitive strategies while teaching reading intermediate level university students. The mind mapping makes the students recall their prior knowledge and use it in the process of reading. Each student's mental map is unique, shaped by prior experiences, motivations, and subjective feelings, resulting in successful navigation in both familiar and unfamiliar texts.

Keywords: reading comprehension, cognition, metacognition, schema theory, memory, mental mapping,

1. Introduction

While dealing with written discourse, readers are often unaware of the cognitive complexity involved in reading process. It involves more than basic interpretation of written discourse and surpasses the simple decoding of words to involve constructing meaning from text, integrating prior knowledge, and applying various *cognitive and metacognitive strategies*. Readers do not merely draw on information from the text but for its interpretation, they also contribute to their own experience and prior knowledge. Research on reading is a multidisciplinary process as it involves psychology, linguistics and education. *This makes reading one of the key skills to be taught to English as second language (ESL) students.*

Reading is a dynamic process that cannot be taught as such. However, depending principally on the learner's ability to learn, it might be facilitated by helping the learners acquire specific strategies that aid their efforts to understand the texts. As Azizifar et al. note "the teaching of reading requires the application of various types of strategies, such as tapping previous knowledge, questions, and making predictions, constructing gist, monitoring, revising meaning, reflecting and relating" (2015, p. 192) which supports an argument that understanding and practicing strategies to interact and engage with the text is necessary for students to become good readers.

2. Cognitive and Metacognitive Learning Strategies in Reading Comprehension

Cognitive strategies are learner-centered approach going beyond linguistic plane and dealing with perceptual, attitudinal, sociological factors. Cognitive strategies facilitate the reader's understanding of written discourse as good readers try to determine the unfamiliar words and concepts before and while reading to begin interpreting text more successfully.

Grabe (1991, p. 379) highlights six general component skills that are used by good readers:

1. *Automatic recognition skills*- a virtually unconscious ability, ideally requiring little mental processing to recognize text, especially for word identification.

2. *Vocabulary and structural knowledge*- a sound understanding of language structure and a large recognition vocabulary.

3. *Formal discourse structure knowledge*- an understanding of how texts are organized and how information is put together into various genres of text (e.g., a report, a letter, a narrative)

4. *Content/word background knowledge* – prior knowledge of text related information and a shared understanding of the cultural information involved in text.

5. *Synthesis and evaluation skills/ strategies*- the ability to read and compare information from multiple sources, to think critically about what one reads, and to decide what information is relevant or useful for one's purpose.

6. *Metacognitive knowledge and skills monitoring*- an awareness of one's mental processes and the ability to reflect on what one is doing and strategies one is employing while reading.

R. Oxford (1990) stated that there are two kinds of learning strategies; direct strategies and indirect strategies. Direct strategies consist of memory strategies, cognitive strategies, and compensation strategies. Meanwhile, indirect strategies consist of metacognitive strategies, affective strategies, and social strategies. While all of these strategies play an important role in language learning, the present article focuses particularly on cognitive and metacognitive strategies, given their central role in reading comprehension.

Reading is a *cognitively complex* process involving coordination of multiple mental functions. It is influenced by attentional control, perception, working memory, and prior knowledge. By using cognitive reading strategies, readers can process information in texts more effectively and understand the author's message. These strategies include making predictions, asking questions, summarizing information, making inferences, visualizing, and answering questions. These strategies help readers obtain, store, and use information from reading more efficiently.

As McNamara (2009) points out, reading strategies are essential to successful comprehension because readers can overcome reading problems in order to become better readers. In other words, *cognitive strategies facilitate the reader's understanding of the information because good readers try to determine the meaning of unfamiliar words and concepts in the text before and while reading in order to begin interpreting information in a text more successfully.*

Skimming strategies

Richards et al. (1992) discovered that the skimming strategy is one of the reading strategies, and it is used when the Wants to get the main idea of ideas from a passage. Skimming is essential for comprehending the general meaning of a passage, comprehending how the passage is structured, the structure of the text, and understanding the writer's intentions. The reader must organize the information and retain some of it because it is not enough to locate it. It is also a writing tool. According to the researcher, *skimming strategies are utilized by readers to obtain a general idea about the content of printed materials by scanning the text.*

Guessing meaning from the text

Contextual guessing is one amongst the foremost important strategies that build learners' vocabulary, and increase their reading comprehension. Bialystok (1983, 2001) stated that this strategy could be used as a compensation one for first and second language reading comprehension, because while reading an overseas text, EFL learners are expected to face *unknown words in the context they are dealing with, they fight to collect information from the encompassing words to urge a general understanding of its meaning.*

Scanning strategies

F. Great (1981) argued that the scanning strategy is a reading technique that utilizes readers to find *specific information without reading the entire text by first looking in at the title, table of contents, and so on.* The researcher believes that the scanning strategy is a type of reading strategy and that it is used to locate specific information. (Md. Harun Rashid, Wang Hui, Jahirul Islam, 2021)

Predicting strategies

Prediction strategy is related to what is expected to happen again in the text. It is achieved by successful readers who mean: they used diagrams, headings, and text and personal knowledge to shape projections before starting to read. (Md. Harun Rashid, Wang Hui, Jahirul Islam, 2021)

Summarization strategy

The summarization technique is one of the reading techniques, *and it is a method of restarting the original*

text's context with one's own words. The findings are usually relatively short and contain the critical point, which summarizes the text succinctly. It is sufficient for stages of high education. This approach includes summarizing the remaining content in a succinct description by consistently extracting unimportant material. Thus, in other words, it is the only tactic readers have left. The details or the fundamental concepts of a given text must be arranged or preserved using the reader's type. (Md. Harun Rashid, Wang Hui, Jahirul Islam, 2021)

Visualizing

Studies have shown that students who visualize while reading have better recall than those who do not (Pressley, 1977). *Readers can take advantage of illustrations that are embedded in the text or create their own mental images or drawings when reading text without illustrations.*

Questioning

Asking and answering questions about text is another strategy that helps students focus on the meaning of text. Teachers can help by modeling both the process of asking good questions and strategies for finding the answers in the text.

Learners "construct knowledge" using cognitive strategies, and they guide, regulate, and evaluate their learning using metacognitive strategies. It is through this "thinking about thinking," this use of metacognitive strategies, that real learning occurs. As students become more skilled at using metacognitive strategies, they gain confidence and become more independent as learners.

Metacognition refers to the knowledge and control that we have over our cognitive processes. On a general level, metacognition includes awareness and control of planning, monitoring, repairing, revising, summarizing, and evaluating. *Essentially, we learn awareness of our comprehension processing.* More specifically, we learn strategies that support our comprehension (our awareness of strategies) and we learn how to carry out these strategies effectively (our control of strategies) (Baker, 2002, 2008; Pressley, 2002). One reason why metacognition is significant is that if learners are not aware of when comprehension is breaking down and what they can do about it, strategies introduced by the teacher will fail. As O'Malley et al. have pointed out: "students without metacognitive approaches are essentially learners without direction or opportunity to review their progress, accomplishments, and future directions" (1985, p. 561).

If cognitive reading strategies are about knowing what strategy to use and how to apply it, then metacognitive strategic knowledge involves understanding the rationale for applying a particular strategy in a particular context, and evaluating its usefulness in terms of appropriacy and effectiveness for that context. Auerbach and Paxton (1997) argue that strategic reading can only become efficient when metacognitive strategies, such as working towards a particular goal while reading, are actively used.

Proficient readers use one or more metacognitive strategies to comprehend texts. There are three main as-

pects of metacognition: metacognitive knowledge, metacognitive monitoring, self-regulation and control (Pintrich, Wolters and Baxter, 2000). The first group consists of cognitive learning strategies which the learner uses to regulate the process of knowledge acquisition. These include, for example, elaboration strategies such as the building of links to prior knowledge, or memory strategies such as note taking. The second group consists of metacognitive control strategies. Central here are activities like the planning and monitoring of learning activities, the evaluation of learning outcomes and the adaptation to varying task demands and (unexpected) difficulties, for example, an increase in directed efforts. In addition to these two groups, which are dominant in research and crucial for the learning process, a third group of strategies in the model developed by Pintrich and Garcia (1994) is dedicated to resource management. These strategies are concerned with the control of the general conditions associated with learning, for example, time management and management of the learning environment

According to Carrell, Gajdusek and Wise (1998), examples of specific metacognitive strategies in reading may include: a) establishing objectives in reading, b) evaluating reading materials, c) repairing miscomprehension, d) evaluating the ongoing understanding of the text, e) analyzing the text and paragraph structure to clarify the author's intention, f) adjusting reading speed and selective cognitive strategies accordingly, and g) engaging in self-questioning to determine if the objectives have been reached. Thus, reading is a metacognitive, as well as a cognitive process. While cognitive strategies refer to deliberate actions that readers take in their efforts to understand texts, metacognitive strategies emphasize the monitoring and regulative mechanisms that readers consciously use to enhance comprehension.

Studies demonstrate that successful comprehension does not occur automatically. Rather, it depends on directed cognitive effort, referred to as metacognitive processing, which consists of knowledge about and regulation of cognitive processing. During reading, metacognitive processing is expressed through strategies, which are "procedural, purposeful, effortful, willful, essential, and facilitative in nature". "The reader must purposefully or intentionally or willfully invoke strategies" (Alexander & Jetton 2000, p. 295), and does so to regulate and enhance learning from text. Through metacognitive strategies, a reader allocates significant attention to controlling, monitoring, and evaluating the reading process (Pressley 2000; Pressley, Brown, El-Dinary, & Afflerbach 1995).

Poor readers are less aware of effective strategies and of the counterproductive effects of poor strategies, and are less effective in their monitoring activities during reading. Adult and college readers who show evidence of metacognitive deficiencies may be the most aware and capable of monitoring their mental processes while reading.

1. Planning

Researchers like Brown and Palincsar (1982) and Zimmerman and Pons (1986) explained that learning needs the capability of planning for learning strategies.

Reading is a three-step pre-reading, reading, and post-reading practice. Zimmerman (2008) described that the objective setting is a procedure to be utilized as a part of the planning stage by calling attention to that while setting testing objectives incite the accomplishment of larger amount execution, setting troublesome objectives is not typically regarded valuable in controlling learners' regulation in Therriault case of objectives may not seem reachable particularly.

2. Monitoring as Metacognitive strategy

Thiede, Anderson, and Therriault (2003) believed that reading and comprehension need to monitor learners' understanding during reading accurately. Self-regulated behavior in reading can be identified through monitoring the text when it is comprehended by the readers. Thiede, Anderson, and Therriault (2003) further asserted that self-regulated learning models help readers to read the text through "learning for the to-be-learned material" philosophy that needs to form a wish to follow for better comprehension. In this strategy, learners do monitor in order to see in what way material is taken for comprehension. Monitoring is used to evaluate the level of readers. If the level of learning is achieved, the readers do leave more learning. If the desired of learning of the readers is not yet achieved, the readers continue reading till its success (Thiede, Anderson, & Therriault, 2003). They further states that there is a need of accuracy in monitoring comprehension of students in order to make them independent learners. Independent or self-regulated readers take responsibility of their own reading and monitor their comprehension level. Most readers reread material in order to answer close reading questions. Schiff and Calif (2004) stated that monitoring in reading is implemented for checking intertextual features that include stylistic features, complex sentence features, and markers in order to integrate novel material for reading comprehension. There are other metacognitive strategies including think-aloud, self-questioning, and self-regulating associated for monitoring of learners' reading and comprehension.

3. Think-Aloud Strategy

Newell and Simon (1972) developed this strategy for evaluation comprehension of the students. Block (1986) called this strategy as problem solving for readers to read and comprehend well by participating in reading actively. Think aloud supports readers to learn through this cognitive strategy related to metacognitive strategies to help students for better performance through thinking and comprehending the text. According to Rosenshine and Meister think-aloud is a scaffolding device for imparting cognitive strategies to make sure of its modeling in comprehension by articulating students' thoughts and their reading loudly to be heard by all peers in class. Rosenshine and Meister (1992) asserted that while learners do practice by questioning through reading task; they are given support by their teachers who model their thinking practices aloud by allowing them to verbalize in the presence of class. Block (1986) considered think-aloud as a strategy to observe the material directly for better reading practices. Anderson (1991) illustrated think-aloud practices

that students employ this cognitive strategy for summarizing and clarifying difficult material in the class.

4. *Questioning Strategy*

Questioning Strategy is used to support students to evaluate their comprehension, to find alternatives, and to raise promising generalities when applying their knowledge freshly learned in class. Benchmark education (2011) stated that expert students are trained to question in terms of the content of material and elaborate their knowledge accordingly. Similarly, Collins and Smith (1982) explained that questioning strategy is used to correct misunderstandings in the reading of the text and in comprehension. However, Livingston (2003) observed that questioning strategy in reading is used to select cognitive knowledge for monitoring the metacognitive activity of reading and comprehension. Rawson, O'Neil, and Dunlosky (2011) suggested

5. Self-analysis having twofold advantages that include:

1) It develops monitoring accuracy of students resulting effectively by controlling the learning and comprehension of the readers.

2) It improves recollection method for collecting or retaining previous concepts learned by readers to be used at the time of need correctly.

6. *Self-Regulating Strategy*

This approach denotes the capability of students to control their learning of reading and comprehension.

According to Zimmerman and Pons (1986) Self-Regulating strategy involves actions directed towards certain goals of the students in order to obtain new knowledge in terms of better comprehension. Further, Gall, Gall, and Borg (2010) observed cognitive strategies and informed that these strategies develop text reading behavior of students and make them self-regulatory for using problem solving methods, self-evaluation, and self-control in learning. Similarly, Brown and Palincsar (1984) proposed two level of reading that includes:

1) Students read fast without any efforts without trying for comprehension the text.

2) Students read slowly and laboriously for better reading by monitoring the whole activity for excelling their comprehension.

However, Chapman (1993) suggested that active readers read slowly with great attention by applying different approaches of cognitive strategies in order to comprehend the material; this depends on individual dissimilarities in reading based on monitoring level.

7. *Evaluating as Metacognitive Strategy*

Evaluating plays a vital role in reading for several purposes. In a few words it is an art of judging the text for specific meaning to be utilized for certain objectives. L. Oczkus (2004) proposed five important factors of evaluation in reading and comprehending material to determine readers with possibility of power in:

1) The importance attained from written manuscript

2) Accuracy in reading and credibility in comprehension

3) Appropriate material

4) Personal attachment with text for enjoyment

5) Self progress in reading

3. **Method and Procedures**

For the purpose of integrating cognitive and metacognitive strategies in teaching Reading in EFL class, we adopted a mixed-methods. The quasi-experimental nature of the study is conditioned by the fact that random assignment of participants was not feasible due to institutional and cultural constraints. The research focuses on examining pedagogical impact of strategy-based reading instructions on ESL students' reading comprehension and metacognitive awareness.

For the purpose of integrating cognitive and metacognitive strategies in teaching via using classroom-based approach with elements of quasi-experimental method and method of mental – mapping or cognitive-mapping.

Mental- mapping method emerged from interdisciplinary research in psychology, geography, and anthropology, highlighting the connection between perception and behavior. As T. Buzan states, mental-mapping is all about the peculiarities of our thinking, since it is not organized linearly, but has a branching structure, each concept in our head is connected with other concepts, these and other concepts are connected with third ones, and so on.(2007)

Using the map, you can delve deeper into the text you are reading, focus on important details, see semantic images, and come up with a topic and idea. It is a technology for displaying information graphically; a tool that allows you to effectively structure information and think using your full creative potential.

The instructional intervention was implemented within a naturally occurring setting during a teaching internship and followed a structured pre-reading, while-reading, and post-reading model. This design allowed the observation of changes in students' reading behavior and written performance over the course of instruction.

Participants of the study

Participants of the study were 11 BA second year students at the English Department in M. Nalbandyan State University of Shirak, during the first semester of 2025/2026 studying a three-credit hour course entitled "English language written and oral language" involving component "Home reading" an 80 minutes meeting once a week session. All students have studied English as a foreign language during the school year from grade 3 to grade twelve.

Instructional Material

Somerset Maugham's short story "The Happy Man" was chosen as an instructional material. The text was chosen for its thematic depth, manageable length, inference-making and discussion in an EFL classroom. The short text associated with short stories motivates students with a basic knowledge of English because it is easier for them to form associations, infer meanings and notice an improvement in reading comprehension. Additionally, short stories are a meaningful resource that enhances critical thinking, reflection and comprehension of new words and expressions in a second language.

Instruments

To collect data on students' reading strategies and metacognitive awareness, a self-report questionnaire

was developed and administered in connection with the reading of W. Somerset Maugham's *The Happy Man*. The questionnaire consisted of both closed-ended and open-ended items. Closed-ended items were rated on a five-point Likert scale and focused on the use of cognitive and metacognitive reading strategies, while open-ended questions encouraged reflection on comprehension, strategy use, and personal response to the text. Although self-report instruments rely on learners' subjective perceptions, they are widely used in reading research to assess strategy awareness and metacognitive processes, which are not directly observable during reading.

In addition to questionnaires mental maps, which was used as qualitative source of data. Mental maps served both as a learning tool and as an indicator of cognitive organization and metacognitive awareness, as students were required to select, structure, and hierarchize information from the story.

Techniques

The instructional intervention was organized according to a three-stage reading model: pre-reading, while-reading, and post-reading. At the pre-reading stage, students were provided with background information about Somerset Maugham, historical, literal, and cultural context in "The Happy Man", and thematic focus of the texts. Cognitive strategies such as prediction and introductory discussions were used to activate prior knowledge and support metacognitive planning.

During the while-reading stage, students engaged in guided reading activities aimed at fostering cognitive strategies such as skimming, scanning, guessing meaning from context, summarizing, and inference-making. Metacognitive monitoring was encouraged through comprehension checks, rereading of challenging passages, and think-aloud activities modeled by the instructor.

At the post-reading stage, students participated in reflective discussions and completed written tasks, including essay writing and the construction of mental maps. While creating mental maps, students visually organized central themes, character traits, and cause-effect relationships in the narrative. This activity promoted synthesis, evaluation, and self-regulation, as learners were required to reflect on their comprehension and make decisions about the relative importance of textual information.

These activities were explicitly designed to activate students' schemata related to Spanish social and cultural values and concepts of happiness depicted in the story.

Results

Questionnaire results revealed frequent use of cognitive strategies such as guessing meaning from context, visualization, and rereading. Majority of the students also reported increased awareness of comprehension breakdowns and strategy adjustment, indicating growing metacognitive control.

Analysis of questionnaire responses revealed noticeable variation in the frequency and quality of strategy use among students. The majority of participants reported frequent use of cognitive strategies such as predicting, guessing meaning from context, rereading

difficult passages, visualization, and activation of background knowledge. These students also demonstrated higher levels of metacognitive awareness, including monitoring comprehension and adjusting strategies when encountering difficulties.

A smaller group of students reported moderate use of reading strategies, selecting "sometimes" for several cognitive and metacognitive items. While these students demonstrated basic comprehension of the text, their essays and mental maps tended to be less detailed and showed more limited thematic development.

Essay analysis demonstrated students' ability to interpret abstract themes such as happiness, freedom, choice, and personal fulfillment. Mental maps showed structured organization of ideas and relationships, with several students revising their maps after rereading, reflecting active monitoring and evaluation.

Analysis of students' mental maps revealed meaningful patterns in how learners organized and interpreted textual information. Most students identified central concepts such as happiness, freedom, choice, and personal fulfillment as key topics, linking them to supporting events, character decisions, and consequences from the story. The structure of the mental maps demonstrated learners' ability to synthesize information and establish hierarchical relationships between ideas, indicating active cognitive processing. Furthermore, the selective inclusion of themes and events suggests metacognitive evaluation, as students had to decide which elements were essential for understanding the text. The use of mental maps also supported comprehension monitoring, as several students reported revising their maps after rereading certain passages. This behavior reflects ongoing metacognitive regulation and awareness of comprehension gaps. Overall, mental mapping proved to be an effective strategy for enhancing both comprehension and reflective engagement with literary texts in an EFL context.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to explore how cognitive and metacognitive reading strategies, supported by schema theory, influence reading comprehension among EFL university students working with a literary text. The findings suggest that explicit strategy-based instruction fosters active engagement with the text, enhances metacognitive awareness, and supports deeper interpretation. One of the central findings is the variation in both the frequency and quality of strategy use among students. Learners who reported frequent use of cognitive strategies such as contextual guessing, rereading, visualization, and activation of background knowledge demonstrated more coherent comprehension outcomes. Their essays reflected interpretive depth, and their mental maps showed structured organization of themes and relationships. This supports Grabe's (1991) assertion that proficient reading involves coordinated use of linguistic knowledge, background knowledge, and higher-order cognitive skills. The results also highlight the critical role of metacognitive strategies in successful reading. Students who monitored their comprehension, reflected on understanding after reading, and adjusted strategies when encountering difficulties showed greater independence

and control over the reading process. This finding aligns with previous research emphasizing that metacognitive awareness distinguishes skilled readers from less skilled ones (Pressley, 2000; O'Malley et al., 1985). In contrast, students who employed strategies inconsistently tended to rely on surface-level comprehension, producing more descriptive than analytical responses. Schema theory provided an effective methodological framework for supporting comprehension of "The Happy Man", a text embedded in a specific cultural context. Pre-reading activities were designed to activate cultural schemata related to Spanish values, lifestyle, and concepts of happiness, facilitated students' ability to interpret characters' choices and motivations. The consistency between students' mental map and essay themes suggests that activating and reorganizing schemata played a key role in meaning construction, supporting the interactive model of reading. The use of mental mapping as a post-reading activity further reinforced both cognitive and metacognitive processes. Mental maps required learners to select, organize, and hierarchize information, thereby encouraging synthesis and evaluation. Students who revised their maps after rereading demonstrated active monitoring and regulation of comprehension, illustrating the recursive nature of strategic reading. These findings support Pintrich's model of self-regulated learning, which emphasizes planning, monitoring, and evaluation as central to effective learning. Importantly, the study indicates that success in reading comprehension is not merely a function of linguistic proficiency but is closely related to learners' strategic awareness and ability to regulate their reading behavior. The observed differences among students suggest that explicit instruction in cognitive and metacognitive strategies can help reduce disparities in comprehension by equipping learners with tools to manage difficulties more effectively. Despite its exploratory nature and small sample size, the study offers pedagogically meaningful insights. The classroom-based design allowed for close observation of learners' reading processes in an authentic instructional setting, supporting the ecological validity of the findings. However, results should be interpreted cautiously and not generalized beyond similar EFL contexts. Overall, the findings reinforce the view that reading is a cognitively and metacognitively driven process in which strategy instruction, schema activation, and reflective tasks such as mental mapping play a crucial role in developing proficient, autonomous readers.

Conclusion

The study examines the role of both cognitive and metacognitive strategies in enhancing English as a foreign language (EFL) intermediate level university students' reading comprehension, with special stress on schema activation and the use of the mental-mapping method. Reading is not a static decoding ability, but a complex dynamic, strategic and self-regulating process. Explicit instruction in cognitive strategies: skimming, scanning, contextual guessing, summarizing and visualization support students in constructing meaning. These strategies become effective when accompanied by metacognitive strategies, including planning, monitoring, self-regulation, questioning, and evaluation. As

a theoretical framework schema theory proves that activation of student's prior knowledge during pre-reading stage facilitated comprehension of "The Happy Man" by S. Maugham, a text embedded in the context of contrasting English and Spanish specific society and culture. Mental mapping emerged as an effective method for integrating cognitive and metacognitive strategies, as this requires the readers to select, hierarchize, and evaluate textual information.

The study suggests that difficulties in reading are not solely attributable to language proficiency, but are closely linked to strategic awareness and the ability to regulate reading behavior. Methods such as mental-mapping combined with strategy-based teaching can help language learners to become more autonomous, confident and effective readers.

In conclusion reading as dynamic multifaceted skill cannot be attributed to one single skill, but results from integration of multiple cognitive and metacognitive strategies, which like the Sun and the Moon are inseparable.

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